

INFLUENCE OF HYGROTHERMAL STRESSES ON
TRANSVERSE CRACK TIP DELAMINATION

Kyohei Kondo
Department of Aeronautics
University of Tokyo
7-3-1 Hongo, Bunkyo-ku, Tokyo 113
Japan

ABSTRACT

It is frequently observed that the fracture of composite laminate under mechanical loading is caused by delamination at tips of transverse crack in the 90° ply due to the strain concentration in the adjacent plies. In the present paper, the influence of hygrothermal loading on the delamination is investigated. Delamination at transverse crack tips in composite laminate subjected to the mechanical and hygrothermal loadings is characterized by the potential energy release rate associated with the delamination growth based on the fracture mechanics. Utilizing the superposition method, the mechanical and hygrothermal loadings are transformed to the mechanical loading applied to the transverse crack surface. And the potential energy release rate is obtained by the classical lamination theory. The delamination onset strain of the graphite-epoxy composite laminate subjected to the uniaxial mechanical loading together with the hygrothermal loading is predicted from the energy release rate, clarifying the influence of the moisture and thermal residual stresses on the fracture of the laminate.

KEYWORDS; Delamination; Transverse Crack; Energy Release Rate; Environment Effect; Classical Lamination Theory

1. INTRODUCTION

A frequently observed failure mode in continuous fiber reinforced laminate composites subjected to mechanical and hygrothermal loadings is delamination between the layers. The common source of the delamination are the laminate free edge and the tip of ply transverse crack running parallel to the fibers of the ply. Unlike the free edge delamination, the transverse crack tip delamination results in the strain concentration in the adjacent plies which leads to the laminate failure.

The onset and growth of delamination can be characterized by the potential energy release rate associated with delamination growth based on the fracture mechanics. The energy release rates for the transverse crack tip delamination in a laminate under inplane mechanical loading has been analyzed by the finite element method utilizing the crack closure technique[1]. And it has been shown that the energy release rate reaches an asymptotic value as the delamination length increases. The asymptotic energy release rate has been obtained by O'Brien[2] based on the compliance change due to the delamination growth. It has been also obtained by Kondo[3,4] by utilizing the superposition method with the results which are somewhat different from those obtained by O'Brien[2].

The asymptotic value of the energy release rate for the free edge delamination in a laminate under mechanical and hygrothermal loadings has been obtained by O'Brien[5] based on the strain energy change due to delamination growth, and by Kondo[6] utilizing the superposition method. In the present paper, the energy release rate for the transverse crack tip delamination in a laminate under mechanical and hygrothermal loadings are obtained by the superposition method. And the influence of the hygrothermal stresses on the delamination onset strain is clarified.

2. UNIFORM STRESSES IN INFINITE LAMINATE

As a basis for analyzing the interlaminar stresses at a transverse crack tip in an infinite laminate by superposition method, the uniform stresses in an infinite laminate without transverse crack are obtained.

The stress-strain relationship for each unidirectional lamina in the laminate is given by

$$\begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_1 \\ \epsilon_2 \\ \gamma_{12} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_{10} \\ \epsilon_{20} \\ \gamma_{120} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} & 0 \\ S_{12} & S_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & S_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \tau_{12} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where the subscripts 1 and 2 correspond to the longitudinal and transverse directions, respectively, of a zero-degree ply. In Eq.(1), the compliance matrix components are expressed in terms of the engineering constants as

$$S_{11} = \frac{1}{E_1} \quad S_{12} = -\frac{\nu_{12}}{E_1} = -\frac{\nu_{21}}{E_2} \quad S_{22} = \frac{1}{E_2} \quad S_{66} = \frac{1}{G_{12}} \quad (2)$$

and the initial strains due to the temperature change ΔT and the moisture content change ΔM are given by

$$\begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_{10} \\ \epsilon_{20} \\ \gamma_{120} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_1 \\ \alpha_2 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \Delta T + \begin{bmatrix} \beta_1 \\ \beta_2 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \Delta M \quad (3)$$

where α_i and β_i are the thermal and hygroscopic expansion coefficients, respectively. The inverse relationship of Eq.(1) is

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \sigma_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{11} & Q_{12} & 0 \\ Q_{12} & Q_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & Q_{66} \end{bmatrix} \left(\begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_1 \\ \varepsilon_2 \\ \gamma_{12} \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{10} \\ \varepsilon_{20} \\ \gamma_{120} \end{bmatrix} \right) \quad (4)$$

which can be transformed to the constitutive equation in the laminate coordinates as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{Q}_{11} & \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{16} \\ \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{22} & \bar{Q}_{26} \\ \bar{Q}_{16} & \bar{Q}_{26} & \bar{Q}_{66} \end{bmatrix} \left(\begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{x0} \\ \varepsilon_{y0} \\ \gamma_{xy0} \end{bmatrix} \right) \quad (5)$$

where the initial strains are given by

$$\begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{x0} \\ \varepsilon_{y0} \\ \gamma_{xy0} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_x \\ \alpha_y \\ \alpha_{xy} \end{bmatrix} \Delta T + \begin{bmatrix} \beta_x \\ \beta_y \\ \beta_{xy} \end{bmatrix} \Delta M \quad (6)$$

For an infinite laminate subjected to uniform mechanical loading and uniform temperature and moisture content changes, the strains are given by the generalized strains as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{\varepsilon}_x \\ \bar{\varepsilon}_y \\ \bar{\gamma}_{xy} \end{bmatrix} + z \begin{bmatrix} \bar{\kappa}_x \\ \bar{\kappa}_y \\ \bar{\kappa}_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = [1 \quad z] \begin{bmatrix} \bar{\varepsilon}_x \\ \bar{\varepsilon}_y \\ \bar{\gamma}_{xy} \\ \bar{\kappa}_x \\ \bar{\kappa}_y \\ \bar{\kappa}_{xy} \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

which coincides with the Kirchhoff hypothesis employed in the classical lamination theory[7]. Substitution of Eqs.(6) and (7) into Eq.(5) gives

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{Q}_{11} & \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{16} \\ \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{22} & \bar{Q}_{26} \\ \bar{Q}_{16} & \bar{Q}_{26} & \bar{Q}_{66} \end{bmatrix} [1 \quad z] \begin{bmatrix} \bar{\varepsilon}_x \\ \bar{\varepsilon}_y \\ \bar{\gamma}_{xy} \\ \bar{\kappa}_x \\ \bar{\kappa}_y \\ \bar{\kappa}_{xy} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{x0} \\ \sigma_{y0} \\ \tau_{xy0} \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

where the initial strains are expressed as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{x0} \\ \sigma_{y0} \\ \tau_{xy0} \end{bmatrix} = - \begin{bmatrix} \bar{Q}_{11} & \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{16} \\ \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{22} & \bar{Q}_{26} \\ \bar{Q}_{16} & \bar{Q}_{26} & \bar{Q}_{66} \end{bmatrix} \left(\begin{bmatrix} \alpha_x \\ \alpha_y \\ \alpha_{xy} \end{bmatrix} \Delta T + \begin{bmatrix} \beta_x \\ \beta_y \\ \beta_{xy} \end{bmatrix} \Delta M \right) \quad (9)$$

The generalized stresses of the laminate are given by

$$\begin{bmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \\ N_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = \int \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{bmatrix} dz \quad (10)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} M_x \\ M_y \\ M_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = \int \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{bmatrix} z dz \quad (11)$$

Substituting Eq.(8) into Eqs.(10) and (11), we have

$$\begin{bmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \\ N_{xy} \\ M_x \\ M_y \\ M_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{16} & B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & A_{26} & B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} \\ A_{16} & A_{26} & A_{66} & B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} \\ \hline B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} & D_{11} & D_{12} & D_{16} \\ B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} & D_{12} & D_{22} & D_{26} \\ B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} & D_{16} & D_{26} & D_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \bar{\epsilon}_x \\ \bar{\epsilon}_y \\ \bar{\gamma}_{xy} \\ \bar{\kappa}_x \\ \bar{\kappa}_y \\ \bar{\kappa}_{xy} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} N_{x0} \\ N_{y0} \\ N_{xy0} \\ M_{x0} \\ M_{y0} \\ M_{xy0} \end{bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

where

$$A_{ij} = \int \bar{Q}_{ij} dz \quad B_{ij} = \int \bar{Q}_{ij} z dz \quad D_{ij} = \int \bar{Q}_{ij} z^2 dz \quad (13)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} N_{x0} \\ N_{y0} \\ N_{xy0} \end{bmatrix} = \int \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{x0} \\ \sigma_{y0} \\ \tau_{xy0} \end{bmatrix} dz \quad (14)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} M_{x0} \\ M_{y0} \\ M_{xy0} \end{bmatrix} = \int \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{x0} \\ \sigma_{y0} \\ \tau_{xy0} \end{bmatrix} z dz \quad (15)$$

For a balanced symmetric laminate, Eq.(12) is reduced to

$$\begin{bmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \\ N_{xy} \\ M_x \\ M_y \\ M_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & 0 & & & \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & 0 & & & \\ 0 & 0 & A_{66} & & & \\ \hline & & & D_{11} & D_{12} & 0 \\ & & & D_{12} & D_{22} & 0 \\ & & & 0 & 0 & D_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \bar{\epsilon}_x \\ \bar{\epsilon}_y \\ \bar{\gamma}_{xy} \\ \bar{\kappa}_x \\ \bar{\kappa}_y \\ \bar{\kappa}_{xy} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} N_{x0} \\ N_{y0} \\ 0 \\ \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

If the laminate is subjected to a unidirectional tensile load, by setting $N_y = N_{xy} = M_x = M_y = M_{xy} = 0$ in Eq.(16), we have

$$\begin{bmatrix} \bar{\epsilon}_x \\ \bar{\epsilon}_y \\ \bar{\gamma}_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{A_{11}A_{22} - A_{12}^2} \left(\begin{bmatrix} A_{22} \\ -A_{12} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} N_x - \begin{bmatrix} A_{22} & -A_{12} \\ -A_{12} & A_{22} \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} N_{x0} \\ N_{y0} \end{bmatrix} \right) \quad (17)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \bar{\kappa}_x \\ \bar{\kappa}_y \\ \bar{\kappa}_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (18)$$

Setting $\bar{\epsilon}_x$ for $N_x=0$ as

$$\bar{\epsilon}_x = \frac{1}{A_{11}A_{22}-A_{12}^2} [A_{22} \quad -A_{12}] \begin{bmatrix} N_{x0} \\ N_{y0} \end{bmatrix} \equiv \bar{\epsilon}_{x^0} \quad (19)$$

in Eq.(17), the tensile load is expressed as

$$N_x = \frac{A_{11}A_{12}-A_{12}^2}{A_{22}} (\bar{\epsilon}_x - \bar{\epsilon}_{x^0}) \quad (20)$$

Thus, for the prescribed tensile load N_x , temperature change ΔT and moisture content change ΔM , the stresses in each lamina of the laminate can be obtained by substituting Eqs.(17) and (18) into Eq.(8). For the prescribed tensile strain, the tensile load N_x in Eq.(17) is given by Eq.(20).

3. SUPERPOSITION METHOD

We analyze the interlaminar stresses in the vicinity of a transverse crack tip in 90° ply of an infinite laminate under uniform tensile load and initial strains due to uniform temperature and moisture content changes as shown in Fig.1 by the superposition method[4].

To obtain an infinite laminate with a ply transverse crack, we make a cut along the plane of $x=0$ in the 90° ply of the infinite laminate subjected to the prescribed mechanical and hygrothermal loadings. As shown in Fig.2(a), the stress distribution of the laminate with the cut can be made identical to that of the original laminate by applying the tractions derived from the stresses of the classical lamination theory in the infinite laminate as

$$[T_x]_{90^\circ} = [\sigma_x]_{90^\circ} \quad (21)$$

to the cut of the 90° ply. Then, as shown in Fig.2(b), we apply the tractions which are of the same magnitude but of opposite sign to those in Fig.2(a) given by

$$[\bar{T}_x]_{90^\circ} = -[\sigma_x]_{90^\circ} \quad (22)$$

to the surface of the transverse crack in an infinite laminate without the mechanical and hygrothermal loadings. The superposition of the load system of Fig.2(a) to that of Fig.2(b) gives the infinite laminate with the free transverse crack surface subjected to the prescribed mechanical and hygrothermal loadings as shown in Fig.2(c).

Since the load system of Fig.2(a) gives no interlaminar stresses, the configuration of Fig.2(b) yields the interlaminar stresses which are identical to those in the transverse crack problem of Fig.2(c). Therefore the configuration of Fig.2(b) represents the transformed transverse crack problem. It should be noted that, even if there exist the delaminations in the infinite laminate without the transverse crack under the uniform mechanical and hygrothermal loadings, the stresses are given by the classical lamination theory. Consequently a laminate with delaminations at the transverse crack tips can also be analyzed through the transformed transverse crack problem.

The tractions applied in the transformed problem are in equilibrium with those applied on the opposite surface of the transverse crack. It implies that the interlaminar stresses exist only in the vicinity of the transverse crack by virtue of the Saint-Venant principle. As one of the advantages of the transformed transverse crack problem, we can easily understand the physical mechanism of the development of the interlaminar stresses by considering the relation between the transformed mechanical tractions applied on the crack surface and the crack tip stresses instead of considering the equilibrium of the tip stresses with the far field stresses due to the mechanical and hygrothermal loadings in the original transverse crack problem.

4. POTENTIAL ENERGY RELEASE RATE

The potential energy release rate associated with the delamination growth approaches to an asymptotic value as the delamination becomes large enough. The asymptotic energy release rate is obtained for the transformed transverse crack problem.

Since the tractions applied to the crack surface are prescribed, the potential energy Π is given by

$$\Pi = U + W = -U \quad (23)$$

in which U and W are the strain energy and the potential energy of the tractions, respectively, and Clapeyron's theorem has been utilized. Therefore, the potential energy release rate associated with the delamination growth da is expressed as

$$G = -\frac{d\Pi}{da} = \frac{dU}{da} \quad (24)$$

for a unit width of the delamination.

Here we consider symmetric delamination growth in the transformed transverse problem as shown in Fig.3. If the delamination length a is large enough, the strain energy increase dU is given by the energy stored in the shaded areas of length da as shown in Fig.3(b). In Fig.3, we assume that

$$\bar{\varepsilon}_y = \bar{\varepsilon}_{xy} = \bar{\kappa}_x = \bar{\kappa}_y = \bar{\kappa}_{xy} = 0 \quad (25)$$

for the regions I and II by considering the constraints from the undelaminated region. Substituting Eq.(25) into Eq.(12) without the initial stresses, we can obtain the resultants contributing to the strain energy in the regions I and II as

$$[N_x]_K = [A_{11}]_K [\bar{\varepsilon}_x]_K \quad (K = I, II) \quad (26)$$

And the strain energy increase is expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} dU &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{K=1}^{\Pi} [N_x]_K [\bar{\varepsilon}_x]_K da \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{K=1}^{\Pi} \frac{([N_x]_K)^2}{[A_{11}]_K} da = \frac{1}{2} ([N_x]_I)^2 \left(\frac{1}{[A_{11}]_I} + \frac{1}{[A_{11}]_{II}} \right) da \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

Substituting Eq.(27) into Eq.(24), we have the potential energy release rate in the form

$$G = \frac{1}{2} ([N_x]_I)^2 \left(\frac{1}{[A_{11}]_I} + \frac{1}{[A_{11}]_II} \right) \quad (28)$$

5. NUMERICAL RESULTS FOR ENERGY RELEASE RATE

The energy release rates associated with the delamination growth at the transverse crack tip were calculated for the graphite-epoxy $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_S$ laminates with the following lamina properties;

$$\begin{aligned} E_1 &= 130.9 \text{ GPa} & E_2 &= 8.934 \text{ GPa} & G_{12} &= 4.648 \text{ GPa} \\ \nu_{12} &= 0.3213 & \alpha_1 &= -0.41 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C} & \alpha_2 &= 26.8 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C} \\ \beta_1 &= 0 & \beta_2 &= 5560 \times 10^{-6}/\text{wt.}\% & t &= 0.14 \text{ mm} \end{aligned}$$

Figures 4, 5 and 6 show the influence of the residual strains due to the temperature change ΔT and the moisture content change ΔM on the energy release rate G in the $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interface of the laminates under the mechanical strains of $\bar{\epsilon}_x - \bar{\epsilon}_x^0 = 0.000, 0.005, \text{ and } 0.010$, respectively. The relations between the energy release rate G and the moisture change ΔM are represented by parabolic curves, and their apexes lying on the horizontal coordinate line shift with the moisture change ΔM and the temperature change ΔT . It can be seen from Fig.4 that, for the laminate without the mechanical loading, the apex shifts leftward with the positive temperature change. As shown in Figs.5 and 6, the apex of the parabolic curve shifts rightward with the increase of the mechanical strain.

Figure 7 shows the delamination onset strain $\bar{\epsilon}_{xcr} - \bar{\epsilon}_x^0$ of the laminate as a function of the moisture change ΔM for various temperature changes ΔT based on the critical energy release rate of $G_{cr} = 90 \text{ N/m}$. It can be seen that the delamination onset strain increases with the increase of the temperature and moisture content changes.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Utilizing the superposition method, the potential energy release rate associated with delamination growth at transverse crack tip in a laminate under mechanical and hygrothermal loadings has been obtained by the classical lamination theory. The influence of the temperature and moisture stresses on the fracture of the laminate has been clarified. The simple closed form expression for the energy release rate for the delamination can serve as the means for selecting the optimum lamination of composites at primary design stage.

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BIOGRAPHY

Kyohei Kondo received Bachelor of Engineering, Master of Engineering and Doctor of Engineering degrees in Aeronautics from University of Tokyo in 1964, 1966 and 1969, respectively. He joined the Department of Aeronautics, University of Tokyo as an Associate Professor in 1973, and has been a Professor since 1983, teaching the mechanics of aerospace structures. He has been currently concerned with research on delamination, creep and vibration of composite laminates.

Figure 1. Transverse Crack in 90° Ply of Infinite Laminate under Mechanical and Hygrothermal Loadings.

Figure 2. Superposition Method for Analysis of Interlaminar Stresses at Transverse Crack Tip of Infinite Laminate.
 (a) Classical Lamination Theory
 (b) Transformed Transverse Crack Problem
 (c) Transverse Crack Problem

Figure 3. Strain Energy Increase dU Associated with Delamination Growth in Transformed Crack Problem.

Figure 4. Energy Release Rate versus Moisture Content Change of Graphite-Epoxy $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_S$ Laminate under Mechanical Strain $\bar{\epsilon}_x - \bar{\epsilon}_x^0 = 0.000$ for Various Temperature Changes.

Figure 5. Energy Release Rate versus Moisture Content Change of Graphite-Epoxy $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_S$ Laminate under Mechanical Strain $\bar{\epsilon}_x - \bar{\epsilon}_x^0 = 0.005$ for Various Temperature Changes.

Figure 6. Energy Release Rate versus Moisture Content Change of Graphite-Epoxy $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_S$ Laminate under Mechanical Strain $\bar{\epsilon}_x - \bar{\epsilon}_x^0 = 0.010$ for Various Temperature Changes.

Figure 7. Delamination Onset Strain versus Moisture Content Change of Graphite-Epoxy $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_S$ Laminate for Various Temperature Changes.